

I. INTRODUCTION

Rias Baixas, a funnel-shaped estuarine inflow system into the coastal drainage area located in NW Spain, is mainly surrounded by Variscan metamorphic and intrusive coastal outcrops (Fig. 1).

Heavy mineral placer occurrences and deposits were formed in coastal areas by weathering of these rocks, such as Balarés Beach (Ponteceso, Coruña; Fig. 2), where ilmenite (Ti), zircon (Zr), cassiterite (Sn), monazite (REE) and other minerals, were extracted between 1941 and 1952.

Subsequently, other marine placer occurrences in the Rias Baixas were studied by IGME (1976 and 1979), Manso et al. (2000), Manso (2001) and more recently by the EU S34I project (Ng-Cutipá et al., 2023; 2024; Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. Geological map of Rias Baixas (NW Spain); syntetized from Rodríguez et al., 2004).

Fig. 2. Pictures of (A) Titania S.A. company and (B) Balarés Beach (Ponteceso, Coruña).

Fig. 3. Placer minerals in (A) Santa Marta and (B) Baluarte (Vao) beaches.

II. OBJETIVE

This study presents the first results of percentages of heavy minerals and geochemical analysis of seven beaches (Límens-Santa Marta, Alemans-Ratas-Canabal and Baluarte-Fontaiña), in the coastal areas of the Vigo Stuary.

III. METHODOLOGY

-Ten sandy-sediment samples were collected in the heavy minerals-enriched surface layer in March 2023. Three different sampling points were taken from 1 cm depth within an area of 1 m².

-Trace elements (Zr, Nb, Hf, Ta, Th, U, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm) were determined by ICP-MS.

-The separation by dense liquid was carried out with bromoform (2,9 g/cm³).

-ICP-MS and XRD analyses were carried out in the IGME laboratory.

IV. RESULTS

1) Surface patches of black and reddish minerals (about 1 to 10 m²) cover the beaches of Santa Marta and Baluarte-Fontaiña (Vao). Below the surface, multilayers (mm to cm) were found to a depth of 50 cm, and the basement is several metres deeper.

2) Ten beach sand samples were analysed from 2023 field trip, showing the predominance of medium to fine fractions (Table 1).

3) Heavy mineral contents in the fine sand fraction, have been quantified up to 46%, considering such placer occurrence to Vao 1, Santa Marta 4 and Ratas 1 samples.

4) Geochemical results for bulk samples show that Vao 1, Santa Marta 4 and Santa Marta 3 samples have the highest contents of Zr, Nb, Hf, Ta, Th, U, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm (Fig. 4). The Ratas 1 sample is also a placer occurrence but has different geochemical values.

5) XRD analyses (heavy mineral fraction) show a predominance of almandine, ilmenite, zircon, tourmaline, staurolite, cassiterite and others (Table 2). Recently, monazite has been identified in stereo microscope and SEM analyses.

Table 1. Granulometry of sands and percentage of heavy minerals in bulk samples

Sample	Granulometry (sand)	Light mineral (%)	Heavy mineral (%)
Límens 1	Coarse to medium	95,32	4,68
Santa Marta 1	Medium to coarse	95,83	4,17
Santa Marta 2	Medium to fine	93,38	6,62
Santa Marta 4	Medium to fine	79,19	20,81
Alemans 1	Coarse to very fine	99,15	0,85
Ratas 1	Fine to medium	89,51	10,49
Canabal 1	Fine to very fine	97,55	2,45
Canabal 2	Fine to very fine	98,44	1,56
Canabal 3	Fine to medium	97,83	2,17
Vao 1	Medium to very coarse	54,01	45,99

Fig. 4. Geochemical results of bulk samples

Table 2. Mineralogical analysis of the heavy mineral fraction

Sample	XRD report
Límens 1	Tourmaline, andalusite, staurolite, ilmenite, phyllosilicates
Santa Marta 1	Tourmaline, andalusite, staurolite, sillimanite, ilmenite, phyllosilicates
Santa Marta 2	Staurolite, tourmaline, ilmenite, andalusite, quartz, phyllosilicates
Santa Marta 4	Staurolite, almandine, ilmenite, zircon, tourmaline, phyllosilicates, pyroxene
Alemans 1	Amphibole, tourmaline, phyllosilicates
Ratas 1	Amphibole, tourmaline, phyllosilicates, quartz
Canabal 1	Amphibole, tourmaline, phyllosilicates, quartz
Canabal 2	Amphibole, phyllosilicates, quartz, tourmaline
Canabal 3	Amphibole, phyllosilicates, tourmaline, quartz
Vao 1	Almandine, staurolite, zircon, ilmenite, andalusite, cassiterite, rutile, tourmaline

V. FINAL REMARKS

1) Surface patches of heavy minerals appear in small sizes in the beachface zone, which is variable along the year caused by tide actions and the season. In addition, subsurface multilayer (mm to cm) up to 50 cm depth shown a potential to accumulate the heavy minerals.

2) Santa Marta and Vao beaches exhibit the highest values of Zr, Nb, Hf, Ta, Th, U, La, Ce, Nd, Sm, and others; associated mainly to heavy minerals (such as almandine, ilmenite, zircon, monazite, tourmaline, staurolite, cassiterite).

3) The placer occurrences in the Rias Baixas show great potential for CRM accumulation, especially close to the sand and crystalline rock substrate contact at the beaches, and in depositional centres in shallow waters areas.

4) Recently field trips between 2023 and 2024, shown quartz and pegmatite veins which can be secondary and local source of heavy minerals in Santa Marta, and Fontaiña-Baluarte (Vao) beaches. Thus, mapping these features therefore improves the knowledge of placer deposits.

5) In addition, other subsoil samples (multi-layered, heavy mineral enriched, Fig. 5) have been collected up to 90 cm depth and are currently being analysed.

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Fig. 5. Enriched layers of heavy minerals in the subsoil of Fontaiña beach, Vigo estuary.

